

EKnad: Exploit Kits' network activity detection

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Abstract

Web Exploit Kits (EKs) are designed to exploit browsers and browsers plugins vulnerabilities, in order to serve malware without drawing user's attention. Despite their longevity, EKs have adapted their modus operandi to new malware trends and pose an imminent threat to individual and organizations. This paper proposes EKnad, a methodology to detect EK exclusively from network-level traces using machine learning algorithms. To capture the network-level behavior of EK, a comprehensive set of features from the network traffic is presented. Moreover, HTTP flows are suitably grouped into the so-called potential EK sessions, in order to improve the detection accuracy and reduce the training time. Using various well-known machine learning algorithms, a comparative experimental study is performed, employing real-world, publicly available network traffic files from 26 different EK families. Numerical results show that the Multilayer Perceptron algorithm outperforms all other machine learning algorithms yielding F1-score equal to 0.983 and at the same time outweighs the detection capabilities of rule-based intrusion detection systems including Snort and Suricata.

Keywords: Exploit Kits, Machine Learning, Multilayer Perceptron, Network Traffic, Snort, Suricata

1. Introduction

The term Exploit Kit (EK), generally, refers to a type of malicious toolkit that is deployed to exploit vulnerabilities in systems and spread malware. In this work, we focus only on EKs that are designed to exploit vulnerabilities on web browsers and their plugins automatically and silently. EKs are monetary-centric frameworks designed to perform drive by download (DBD) attacks [1], which can infect computerized systems with any type of malware (e.g., keyloggers, trojans, etc.), while visiting a website. The victim does not have to perform any action (for instance, to click a link), except for visiting the website and the DBD attack will be performed as a background process. The EK authors employ various techniques to lure a victim to visit the EK's web page [2]. In particular, the three major infection vectors are:

1. **Malvertising:** Malvertising refers to malicious advertisements that are placed on popular websites. The EK authors can issue an account that allows them to upload custom-designed advertisements, which are published online via the advertising provider. They carefully place malicious code inside the advertisements that will silently redirect the visitors of the website to the EK web page.
2. **Compromised web pages:** EK authors crawl the internet to identify security-weak websites in order to abuse them and inject malicious content into their web server [3]. The malicious content could be, for instance, an HTML element

called iframe (inline frame) that redirects the unsuspecting visitor to the EK web page.

3. **Social engineering:** EK authors deploy social engineering techniques, like phishing or spear-phishing emails that contain an attachment or a link that points to the EK web page.

1.1. Problem Statement and Motivation

As the browser is the main gateway to access the Internet, it continues to evolve to suit the needs of the worldwide web and modern web applications. At the same time browser's functionality is ever-expanding through the use of plugins introducing new computing paradigms. For example, the Chrome OS is an operating system solely based on the Chrome browser. As the complexity and the functionality of browsers increase, it is evident that the attack surface also increases. As a matter of fact, multiple vulnerabilities have been discovered in browsers and significant attacks against insecure plugins have made headlines over the years [4]. Browser vulnerabilities may expose users' data and lead to catastrophic consequences from stealing passwords and credit cards to silently load malware and gain remote access [5]. Thus, it is expected that browsers will continue to be the prime target of cyber-criminals utilizing EKs to exploit vulnerabilities and attack end-users.

Moreover, a recent, large-scale study of EKs functionalities presented in [6] concluded that a common trait of EKs is their ability to quickly adapt to new malware trends. Indeed, nowadays EKs have evolved and shifted their modus operandi to more lucrative methods by delivering ransomware. For instance, the Maze ransomware was initially delivered through spam email campaigns, but cybercriminals changed their tactics by taking advantage of EKs to infect computers. Due to

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the rise of the popularity of cryptocurrencies, EK authors have also shifted their focus to distribute cryptocurrency mining malware, which is classified as a new attack type called Drive-By-Mining (DBM) to deliver cryptojacking malware [7]. Another interesting finding in [6] was that EKs pose a significant threat, due to their intelligence to bypass contemporary security countermeasures. One such example is the fact that EKs have evolved beyond file-based methods, with malicious files now existing as memory processes in the operating system in order to evade detection (file-less payloads). This makes even more challenging the detection of EKs at the host level as the delivery payload does not touch the disk and leaves no room for antivirus technology to detect EKs [8]. Thus, we conclude that despite their longevity, EKs are still relevant in the underground malware market as they evolve by adapting to new malware trends. A recent report from MalwareBytes [9] published in 2020 highlighted that incidents of EKs are on the rise by a new generation of EKs that have adopted more sophisticated techniques to evade security mechanisms and distribute malware in covert ways. According to McAfee, many new EKs such as Spelevo, Capesand, Lord, Fiesta, and Fallout were discovered in 2019. At the time of writing this work, a new EK has emerged named Purple Fox that includes several 1-day exploits such as CVE-2021-26411 and CVE-2020-0674 [10]. The research community has been also active in this area (as we analyze in Section 3), while the latest works (i.e., published in 2020 & 2021) analyze EKs from various point of views including browser forensics, detection methodologies, and the role of underground economy in the continuous development of EKs [11], [12], [13], [14], [15]. Overall, we argue that the problem of EKs still poses a viable threat to both individuals and organizations.

EKs that utilize File-less malware are harder to detect, since they do not leave detection traces at the file system and resides only in the host memory. Besides, other evasion techniques can be applied including obfuscation and encryption to bypass host based defensive mechanisms. Thus, new effective detection technologies are needed to curb the ongoing threat of EKs. Considering the above observations, this paper will seek answers to the following research problem: *Can we build robust EK detection systems that are capable of efficiently detecting state-of-the-art EKs based on traces at the network level operation of EKs?* The key insight here is that the HTTP network flows of EKs include a wealth of information that after careful processing can be turned into actionable data for EK detection.

1.2. Contributions

This paper presents a Machine Learning (ML) methodology, named EKnad (Exploit Kits' network activity detection) that can detect EK infection activity by analyzing the network traffic from packet captures. More specifically, EKnad contains two phases, the *Pre-processing* and the *EK detection*. The *Pre-processing* phase first extracts the HTTP communication from the network traffic. Second, it creates potential EK sessions by grouping the HTTP flows aiming to the better and faster identification of EKs redirection chains. Following, the *EK detection* phase extracts discriminating features from the potential

EK sessions and feeds them to ML algorithms for EK classification between EK or benign. We propose a comprehensive set of 47 different features, to cover all the infection steps of EKs, which are divided into 5 categories: Header, Redirection, Evasion, URL & Domain, and Connection. To evaluate EKnad, we deployed publicly available EK network traces from 26 different EK families to perform four rigorous and diverse evaluation experiments. Special care was taken so that our evaluation methodology complies with state-of-the-art guidelines that should be followed when evaluating ML algorithms to avoid misleading and erroneous results. Numerical results show that EKnad achieves the best detection performance with the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) Artificial Neural Network classifier outperforming other ones (i.e., Random Forest, Bayesian Network, Decision Table, k-Nearest Neighbors, J48). EKnad is able to detect new and last-generation EKs based on the training of older EKs, as well as to detect less-known EK families based on the training of well-known EK families. In addition, EKnad outperforms famous rule-based intrusion detection systems including Snort and Suricata. In summary, our contributions lie in the following aspects:

- We define a novel term named *potential EK session* that groups HTTP flows based on the attack patterns of EKs to improve the detection performance.
- We propose and elaborate on a comprehensive feature set that is exclusively derived from the network traces and captures the network-level behavior of EKs.
- We propose a novel ML detection methodology that focusing on the HTTP traffic considers all the infection steps of EKs to effectively detect them.
- We elaborate on a set of state-of-the-art rules and guidelines for the objective and accurate evaluation of EKnad classifiers. The related work has often neglected to follow these rules leading to biased and erroneous results.
- We comprehensively evaluate EKnad under real world scenarios. We use an imbalanced dataset that includes 26 different EK families and show that our methodology achieves high detection performance on several evaluation metrics (i.e., at least 0.983 accuracy, 0.065 FPR, 0.984 recall & precision, 0.983 F1-score, 0.949 MCC, and 0.996 AUC) with the MLP classifier.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 elaborates on background knowledge for EKs, while Section 3 presents the related works highlighting their advantages and drawbacks. Section 4 analyzes the EK network traffic and discusses the network-level detection features. Section 5 analyzes the EKnad detection methodology. Section 6 evaluates EKnad and presents the results of the experiments. Finally, Section 7 summarizes the critical points and outlines the conclusions.

2. Background

This section briefly describes the EKs' infection procedure to facilitate readers, who are not familiar with EKs to comprehend the presented notions.

2.1. Exploit Kits

EKs are software tools that provide an automatic exploitation environment for computer systems. They detect and exploit web browser vulnerabilities to deliver malicious payloads (i.e., malware) without drawing the victim’s attention [16]. EK authors have evolved the DBD attack process by developing a business model, which is similar to the software-as-a-service paradigm. Namely, EK customers can purchase subscriptions on a pay-per-install model and choose a plethora of functions (e.g., number of exploits or malware) [17] to harm personal computers via the browser. The popularity of EKs highly depends on their price, their distribution network, as well as their functions. Moreover, EKs put emphasis on user-friendliness to attract more clients. For instance, they provide a management console with a graphical user interface that automates the exploitation and infection processes, hence there is no need for EK users to be computer experts.

In the following, the EK workflow is described (see Figure 1): (1) The procedure starts with the attacker that compromises a legitimate web page by placing malicious content (or sets up a malicious website); (2) The victim visits the compromised web page and the browser renders the malicious content; (3) The malicious content silently redirects the victim to the EK server. The EK server fingerprints (i.e., gather information about the operating system, browser version, plugins, geolocation, and language) the victim browser to determine if it is vulnerable and selects the appropriate exploit; (4) Based on the identified vulnerabilities, a suitable exploit is selected and is delivered to the victim’s browser (if there are multiple vulnerabilities, multiple exploits may be executed); (5) In case of successful exploitation, the victim’s browser replies accordingly. In case of unsuccessful exploitation, the EK server delivers the next suitable exploit; (6) The browser unwillingly downloads what is known as a “payload”, which is the malware binary file; (7) Lastly, the malware is executed and the host is infected.

Figure 1: Exploit Kit infection procedure

Moreover, EKs employ several advanced features to evade detection mechanisms, making them stealthier and hiding their infection activity. These features are:

1. HTTP 302 cushioning: Some EKs (e.g., Blackhole, Angler, Neutrino) utilized a technique known as HTTP 302 cushioning where the EK authors exploit the legitimate HTTP 302 response to create a sequence of redirects through proxy domains before the victim is redirected to the EK landing page

(the first page that the victim visits in the EK server). This technique removes the need for iframes, which are heavily used by EKs to redirect the victim to the EK landing page, and relies on a legitimate browser feature hardening the EK detection process.

2. Obfuscation: EKs employ obfuscation techniques to their code to avoid detection by malware scanners. The obfuscation techniques that EK deploy are randomization, string obfuscation, string concatenation, character substitution, polymorphic obfuscation, etc. [18]. The obfuscated code is updated frequently, as the EK authors check whether the signature of the obfuscation scheme is already known. An interesting fact is that some EKs authors use commercial obfuscation software (e.g., IonCube) to protect the EK source code [19].
3. Cloaking: Many EKs advanced the fingerprinting process by inspecting the IP address and the system information to target only certain countries or identify addresses that are related to honeypots and security vendors. In case that a victim does not meet the selected criteria, the EK process will not take place and it will redirect the victim to a legitimate web page or it will display an HTTP 404 error. In addition, in case that the system is not vulnerable the EK will redirect the victim to a legitimate web page [20].
4. Blacklist avoidance: EKs deploy Domain Generation Algorithms (DGA) to constantly change the domain names. This is done periodically or when an IP/URL is disclosed to a known blacklist. Recent EK authors deployed a technique named “Domain Shadowing”, where they hijack domain registrant accounts and create many seemingly random subdomains [21].

2.1.1. Exploit Kits Impact on Cyberscrime scene

Several EKs are considered successful as they have been proved to be profitable for cybercriminals. Blackhole was the first sophisticated EK that adopted the rental business model and a reference point for newer EKs. Its key features were the advanced evasion techniques (i.e., server-side polymorphism, JavaScript & HTML obfuscation, and string manipulation techniques). Along with Blackhole, other infamous EKs emerged such as the Nuclear and Angler EK.

Rig EK is one of the most successful EK so far since it was first introduced in 2014 and at the time of writing is still active. In 2015, Rig was responsible for the infection of approximately 27,000 machines per day¹. Its low price when it was first released contributed to gain popularity quickly. Rig adopts Blackhole’s business model and its monthly subscription prices range from \$700 to \$2000. The Rig EK have used domain shadowing, while nowadays Rig delivers mostly ransomware and crypto-miners.

New EKs still emerge [22] showing that EKs activity is difficult to be ceased. The Fallout EK is a relatively new EK, which appeared in the August of 2018. It is being served via

¹<https://www.trustwave.com/en-us/resources/blogs/trustwave-blog/how-an-upgraded-version-of-the-rig-exploit-kit-is-infecting-27k-computers-per-day/>

malvertising campaigns that affected users mostly in Japan, Korea, Middle East, and Southern Europe. Fallout EK targets vulnerabilities on Internet Explorer browser (e.g., CVE-2018-8174) and Flash Player (e.g., CVE-2018-15982), while its malware list is comprised of ransoms, banking trojans, and information stealers. Spelevo EK was first seen in mid-2019 and delivers various banking trojans (e.g., IcedID and Dridex). Lord EK is also one of the newest EKs, as it was noticed in August 2019, and delivers the ERIS ransomware and the trojan njRAT. The most recent EK (appeared in 2021) is named Purple Fox that includes several browser exploits such as CVE-2021-26411 and CVE-2020-0674.

3. Related Work

This section elaborates on previous works that focus on EKs or DBD attacks highlighting their limitations and describing how the limitations have been addressed in this paper. We can classify the related works in three categories based on the data source that deploy to detect or study EKs: i) network traffic (i.e., logs, PCAP files), ii) EK server-side source code (i.e., PHP), iii) and EK client-side source code (i.e., HTML, JavaScript, etc.).

3.1. Network Traffic

In the network traffic category, Mekky et al. [23] were among the first that exploit the HTTP redirection chains for the detection of DBD attacks (upon which EKs are based). To achieve this, the authors built a per-user browsing activity tree, which maintains all the redirection chains that are triggered by an HTTP request. Moreover, they deploy a Decision Tree classifier (J48) to detect the malicious HTTP redirection chains. The experiments showed high detection accuracy from 99.1% up to 99.9%. An extension of the above work presented in [24], in which the HTTP packets are dissected and reassembled into bidirectional TCP flows to perform tree-based similarity searches. The authors concluded that their method outperforms the state-of-the-art in terms of false positive and false negative rates. Both of the aforementioned works rely solely on the redirection URLs to perform the detection. Moreover, the dataset in [23] is limited while in [24] the authors do not take advantage of ML and overlook to consider several other characteristics of EKs.

Towards this direction, Nikolaev et al. [25] present a method that detects EKs' by deploying traits entirely from HTTP proxy logs. Five traits were extracted from the HTTP proxy logs and fed in the detection algorithm and used regular expressions to classify the malicious activities in one of the following EK families: Angler, Neutrino, and Rig. The results were promising, however, the authors relied their evaluation only on three EK families. Moreover, the extracted traits did not take into account the whole infection procedure of EKs, as well as they did not consider an important trait of EKs, namely the chain of redirections, as they concentrate on a single malicious HTTP request/response pair to detect EKs. Qin et al. [15] relied on HTTP header information to build a graph model from which they extracted EK detection features including several

graph-specific features such as node centrality, longest path, etc. The evaluation performed on a dataset that contains 9362 EK and 10541 benign network traffic files using 10-fold cross-validation. The Random Forest classifier accomplished the best detection performance, namely 94.9% accuracy. The deployed dataset contains a large number of EK PCAP files (9362 in total) from two websites, (1) malware-traffic-analysis.net [26] (993) and (2) threatglass.com (8369). Although the proposed solution attains high detection accuracy, the utilized dataset in the experiments has several pitfalls. In particular, several EK PCAP files from malware-traffic-analysis.net website include the same EK running in a different environment, which means that the obtained dataset does not include unique samples. Furthermore, the EK PCAP files of the threatglass.com website (which is not accessible anymore, hence the 8369 EK samples cannot be verified) may appeared also in [26], namely duplicated samples may be included in the dataset. Also, the authors did not provide any information regarding the utilized EKs families neither whether they tried to detect EKs from the same family, fact that may significantly improve the detection results, since EKs of the same family do not have many differences. Finally, the ratio between benign and EK samples of the training and testing datasets is approximately the same. This balanced dataset does not represent a realistic scenario, since benign network traffic is higher than malware traffic with EKs.

A recent study that has the same grounds with EKnad is presented in [27]. The authors proposed an ML approach for the classification of EKs based on EK network traffic files (PCAP). The EK files were used as input into the Zeek (known as Bro) IDS² to create network flows and extract from them various content-based, interaction-specific, and connection-specific features from the HTTP, DNS, and File logs. They deployed a Decision Tree classifier, which detected the EK traffic and the EK families with 97.74% accuracy. The paper does not evaluate other classifiers, while the number of the considered EK families is limited to five. Towards this direction, Burgess et al. [28] also deployed the Zeek IDS to extract HTTP redirection chains from EKs network traffic. In their study, the authors identified nine redirection techniques and they were able to extract 96.52% of the EK domains. The authors' main goal was to generate HTTP redirection features and not to propose a full-fledged EK detection solution. In their newer work, Burgess et al. [14] deployed the 1279 EK and 5910 benign redirection chains that were identified in [28] to detect EKs using an LSTM RNN classifier. The classifier attained 0.9878 F1-Score using only redirection features. The authors did not provide a comprehensive solution since they focused only on one trait of EKs (i.e., the redirection) as well as they did not compare the proposed classifier with other well-known ML classifiers to validate its detection performance. Furthermore, it is unclear from how many EK PCAP files the authors concluded to 1279 EK redirection chains.

²<https://www.zeek.org/>

3.2. EK Server-Side Source Code

The second category contains research works that focus on the EKs' server-side source code to extract useful information that may facilitate EKs detection or the understanding of their attack techniques. Eshete et al. [29] proposed WebWinnow, a system that deploys supervised ML models to detect whether a given URL is hosting an EK. WebWinnow deploys in total 30 features extracted from the source code of 38 EKs. These features were separated into 4 categories: Aggregate-Behavioral, Interaction-Specific, Connection-Specific, and Content-Specific. The authors claim that WebWinnow using a Decision Tree (J48) classifier achieved 99.9% true positives and 0.1% false positives in the testing phase. On the other hand, in PEXy [21], the authors applied static analysis on the EKs' source code to examine how the utilized exploits will be triggered. PEXy was able to provide all the necessary conditions to provoke all exploits and detect all the paths to malicious output from EKs with very few false positives and false negatives. Finally, EkHunter [30] is a toolkit that aims to compromise EK servers by performing a vulnerability analysis on the source code of EKs. The authors surveyed 30 EKs and found over 180 vulnerabilities in 16 EKs, while they managed to exploit 6 of them. A fundamental limitation of the above-mentioned research works is the scarce availability of EKs source code, as the only way to obtain it is when the authorities cease the EK activities and release the EK source code.

3.3. EK Client-Side Source Code

The third category, namely client-side source code, mostly examines the malicious JavaScript code that is heavily deployed by DBD attacks and EKs. Curtsinger et al. [31] proposed Zozzle, a JavaScript malware detector that is deployed in the browser. Zozzle combines a JavaScript Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) with a Naive Bayes classifier. The experimental results showed 99.45% detection accuracy and a very low FPR. CUJO [32], is a detection and prevention system for DBD attacks that transparently inspects web pages and blocks the delivery of malicious JavaScript code. CUJO was implemented as an extension to a web proxy and combines static and dynamic analysis of the JavaScript code and a Support Vector Machines (SVM) classifier to detect malicious code. Both Zozzle and CUJO focus only on the JavaScript code to extract detection features which is a challenging task since EK authors constantly try to discover new obfuscation techniques to hide their code. Based on the same principles, Canali et al. [33] presented Prophiler, a lightweight filter for DBD attacks, which deploys static analysis techniques to quickly examine a web page for malicious content. Prophiler filters non-malicious pages so that malicious pages can be examined more extensively by honeypots. To evaluate Prophiler, the authors used the Random Forest classifier for HTML features, whilst for JavaScript & URL and host-based features, they deployed a Decision Tree classifier (J48). The proposed solution can be considered as a filter that performs an initial check on web pages rather than a detection system.

FriSM [34] is a detection model for EKs based on string-similarity matching. The authors introduced features belonging

to three classes: probabilistic (e.g., number of words, JavaScript functions, etc.), size-based (e.g., web page file size, string size, etc.), and distance-based (e.g., the ratio of alphanumeric characters, code string similarity, etc.). The aforementioned features were extracted from the EKs network traffic and deployed to measure whether they are similar to patterns generated by EKs activities. Although the results were promising, FriSM is sensitive in terms of false positives and the string-similarity matching technique requires a similar structure between different EK families to be accurate. In case that the EKs' structure changes, the extracted features will not be informative and patterns can not be created. In [11], the authors introduced a visualization approach for the detection of EKs. In particular, the EK source code (the paper claims that both client-side code such as JavaScript and server-side code such as PHP are utilized) were converted into gray-scale images and the authors observed that different EK families have different code schemes, which result in different images. A convolutional NN classifier was used to detect the EKs. With this approach, the authors accomplished very high detection performance combined with low detection time. However, a general limitation of malware detection based on image classification is that it can be easily evaded by adding garbage code.

To summarize, the works of the network traffic category utilize a limited number of features to detect EKs. In the server-side source code category, a fundamental limitation is that the source code of EKs is not publicly available, thus it is difficult for these works to be applied in a generic manner. In the client-side source code category, the authors focus on the JavaScript and HTML code for EKs detection, which is easily evaded. However, EKs can easily change their obfuscation techniques making detection on the source code level very hard. Overall, when it comes to the evaluation, previous works (regardless of their category) share common limitations, such as considering a small number of unique EK families in the datasets or experiments performed on balanced datasets that are not representative of EKs in the wild. To address the identified limitations of the existing works, we propose EKnad, a holistic methodology for the detection of EKs using a rich feature set that is extracted from the network traffic. By evaluating several ML classifiers using state-of-the-art rules and guidelines and representative samples of various EK families (i.e., 26 different EK families), we are able to detect old and more recent EKs using imbalanced datasets in multiple evaluation scenarios.

4. Exploit Kits Network Analysis and Proposed Features

To detect EK activity promptly and accurately, we argue that the network traffic includes a wealth of information that can be utilized for the detection of EK presence. Particularly, our intuition is that EKs follow an attack pattern, that is a victim is redirected in a compromised website, and subsequently redirected to an EK server, which initiates the exploitation of the victim's browser and concludes with the payload delivery. This sequence of events leaves behind tracks on the HTTP protocol from which we can extract discriminating features of EKs'

activities. Based on the above observations we define the following 5 feature categories:

1. EKs generate HTTP requests and responses, which employ specific *header features* to perform specific malicious actions. For instance, to exploit a Java vulnerability in the browser, they deploy the Content-Type: application/java-archive header.
2. Before delivering the malware, EKs perform multiple redirects to infect a victim's computer. Consequently, several *redirection features* are generated. Previous works have also considered this EK function [22], [23].
3. Elaborating more on the HTTP traffic, we observed that EKs hide their presence by deploying *evasion features*, which mainly refer to the encoding of the web pages' contents.
4. EKs' web pages contain *URL & Domain features* that are equivalent in all EK families and different from the benign web pages (e.g., the EKs' domain names entropy appeared to be higher than the benign domain names).
5. Finally, *connection features* are a part of EKs' network activity. We noticed that as EKs perform specific actions, hence they generate a specific number of HTTP GET and POST requests. In contrast, in benign activity this number is arbitrary. Consequently, the average number of HTTP requests and responses differ in EK and benign network activity.

The aforementioned 5 feature categories are extracted from all steps of EK infection procedure (i.e., Steps 2-6 of Figure 1). However, it is important to mention that there are some specific features that are based on the EK redirection procedure (i.e., Step 2 of Figure 1) such as Location Header or Referer header, while other features are exclusively based on the EK exploitation procedure (i.e., Steps 4-6 of Figure 1) such as Content-Type: application/java-archive. For clarity, the features that are utilized only in the exploitation steps are highlighted in the description below. It should be also mentioned that some of the features have been also considered in the literature [27], [28], [29].

Based on the above 5 feature categories, we analyze now the proposed EK detection features. The *Header Features* category is comprised of HTTP headers that appeared in the HTTP requests and responses between the EK and the victim. The *Redirection Features* category encompass various features, such as HTTP redirection, URL parameter redirection, etc., which are occurred during the redirect from the compromised website to the EK server. The *Evasion Features* category represents the advanced obfuscation techniques that EKs employ. The *URL & Domain Features* are based on suspicious traits that appear in the format of the URLs and in the domain names as utilized by EKs [35]. In the HTTP traffic, we observed patterns also in URLs as well as domains associated with EKs. The *Connection Features* category is comprised of features of the HTTP traffic in general (e.g., number of HTTP GET requests, number of HTTP responses, etc.). Please note that the proposed features can be also present in benign traffic. For example, the Content-Type: application/octet-stream feature (see below) is present in both benign and EK traffic. For this reason, none of the proposed features can be used standalone for detection. Moreover, some of the proposed features are (or

have been) utilized frequently by several EKs. For example, the Content-Type: application/java-applet has been utilized for the exploitation of Java applets by EK families, such as Blackhole, Neutrino, and Nuclear. However, EKs do not rely only on one specific exploit and continuously try to adapt their exploitation strategy according to the latest exploits available. This also corroborates the combination of multiple features for detection. Below we analyze the proposed features for each feature category. Please note that the notation used to count the features includes the first letter of the feature category followed by two letters of the subcategory (if there is any subcategory) followed by the digit counter. For example, the H.CT.1 is the first feature of the Header (H) category that includes the Content Type (CT) subcategory.

Header Features: This feature category contains only binary features, namely whether the features are presented in the network traffic.

H.CT Content-Type:

H.CT.1 text/html: The text/html header is used to inform the browser that the content of the served web page is HTML.

H.CT.2 application/java-archive: This header refers to Java archive (jar) files and is usually deployed by EKs to send a Java exploit in the browser. Hence it is utilized in the EK infection step 4 as depicted in Figure 1.

H.CT.3 application/javascript: The application/javascript header is used to understand the browser that the received content contains JavaScript code.

H.CT.4 application/java-applet: This feature indicates that the HTTP message delivers a Java applet, which is located on the EK server and is executed on the web browser of the victim. Some well-known EK families, such as Blackhole, Neutrino and Nuclear, utilized Java applets to exploit Java vulnerabilities (e.g., CVE-2012-468 and CVE-2013-2463). The Content-Type: application/java-applet header is utilized in the EK infection step 4 as presented in Figure 1.

H.CT.5 application/octet-stream: This HTTP header is used to indicate that an HTTP message contains arbitrary binary data. This header is often used by benign websites to convey data to the browser such as applications, documents, images, etc. When it comes to EKs, they have utilized it to deliver malware in the form of a Windows executable files (.exe). Typically, EKs combine the headers Content-Type: application/octet-stream and Content-Disposition: attachment (H.CD), in order to directly download malware into the victim's computer. The Content-Type: application/octet-stream has been applied also in previous works for the detection of EKs [29]. This feature represents the EK infection step 6 as highlighted in Figure 1.

H.CT.6 application/xml: This Content-Type header is used to serve xml data in the browser. We observed that this header is used by various EK web pages.

H.CT.7 application/x-shockwave-flash: This header indicates that the web page transmits a Small Web Format (swf) file, which is basically an Adobe Flash file. We no-

ticed that many EKs target Adobe Flash vulnerabilities and send swf files to exploit them. This header is used in the EK infection step 4 as shown in Figure 1.

- H.CT.8 application/x-silverlight-app: This header is Microsoft’s equivalent of the application/x-shockwave-flash header and it is used to send .xap files.
- H.CT.9 application/postscript: The application/postscript header is used to deliver a PostScript (ps) file in the browser. EKs deploy ps files to exploit the related victim’s browser plugins.
- H.CT.10 application/pdf: This header is utilized to serve malicious pdf files to exploit related browser plugins.
- H.CT.11 application/x-msdownload: This header is commonly used to indicate whether a DLL file is presented in an HTTP response message and it delivers .exe files. We observed that some EK families deploy the x-msdownload header to deliver a malware, hence this header is employed in the EK infection step 6 of Figure 1.
- H.CT.12 application/x-msdos-program: This header is deployed to denote the presence of an “MS DOS” application or executable file in an HTTP response. EKs usually employ this header for malware delivery purposes.
- H.CT.13 application/x-dosexec: This header is a subtype of Content-Type: application/x-msdownload and it is also used to deliver .exe files.
- H.UA User-Agent: EKs only target browsers and their plugins [19], hence the HTTP traffic that does not contain a User-Agent header that points to a known web browser (e.g., Internet Explorer, Google Chrome, Firefox, Safari, etc.) it is not related with EK activity [21].
- H.CD Content-Disposition: attachment: When this header is used in an HTTP response, it prompts the user to save the response of a web page as a file. During the analysis of the EKs’ network activity, we observed that this header is deployed by EKs along with H.CT.5 to download a file in the victim’s computer. Thus, this header is also deployed in the EK infection step 6 as illustrated in Figure 1.
- H.CE Content-Encoding: This header is used to compress the media type of the HTTP message.

Redirection Features: In this category, we extracted features from the URL and the Header fields of the HTTP traffic that are related to redirects from one webserver to another. We did not extract features from the web page contents as they can be obfuscated and reduce the detection performance of the classifier.

- R.1 HTTP Redirection: HTTP redirects are commonly used by web developers to redirect the user to a different URL than the one they initially tried to access. Modern browsers automatically and transparently redirect their users when they receive a 301, 302, 303, 304, or 307 HTTP response (see also Section 2.1).
- R.2 Location Header: The Location header field contains the URL that the user is going to visit after the redirection. This field forces a web browser to load a different web page than the one that is already opened. We identified the Location header in the network activity of several

EKs.

- R.3 Referer Header: The Referer (originally a misspelling of the word “referrer”) header identifies the address of the web page that originates the request. In case that the domain in the Referer header is not the same with the domain in the HTTP Host header, then the request came from a different domain. We extract as a feature the presence of a Referer header that includes a different domain than the one in the Host header.
- R.4 URL Parameter Redirection: The last redirection feature we extract from the HTTP traffic is the URL parameter-based redirection. Web pages could redirect a browser to a different web page via a URL parameter. This feature is also deployed in [33].

Evasion Features: A strong trait of EKs is their robustness, which is achieved with evasion techniques. We have identified two binary features that EKs deploy to obfuscate their activity.

- E.1 JavaScript Obfuscation: 95% of EKs deploy obfuscation techniques to their JavaScript code [29]. To detect obfuscated JavaScript code, we searched in the EK network activity for the three most common techniques deployed for JavaScript obfuscation. These techniques are:
 - **Randomization Obfuscation.** It replaces the names of variables and functions with randomly created sequences of characters that have no particular meaning, thus we searched for an unreadable sequence of characters.
 - **Encoding Obfuscation.** It converts parts of the code into hexadecimal representations, namely, it encodes the variable’s values and the inputs that are passed into functions. We seek hexadecimal representations.
 - **Dead Code Insertion.** It adds arbitrary code that is executed during the execution of the initial code without affecting its semantics, hence we look for arbitrary code parts.
 - E.2 HTML Obfuscation: We observed in the network traffic that EKs utilize also obfuscation techniques to hide the HTML code. The most common techniques for HTML obfuscation are the HTML entities encoding and the base64 encoding. We searched for the aforementioned techniques in HTTP responses that contain the Header Content-Type: text/html.
- URL & Domain Features:** EKs’ network traffic utilizes URL and domain names features that deviate from benign network traffic. This category is comprised of binary, integer (by counting the occurrence of a feature), or a real number value.
- U.1 Max URL length: The length of the URL could provide insights regarding whether the URL is benign or malicious. To this end, we extract as a feature the maximum length of the URLs that appeared in the network activity.
 - U.2 Max URI directory depth: This feature indicates the maximum directory depth extracted from the URIs of the network activity.
 - U.3 IP address in the URL: It is common for malicious and EK web pages to be associated with an IP address instead of using a domain name. This feature tracks if instead of a domain name, an IP address is present in at least one

URL of the network activity.

- U.4 Suspicious filename in the URL: This feature depicts the presence of a randomly generated string or a common filename inside the network activity. Many EKs utilize automatically generated filenames, which are composed of random strings. Moreover, EKs share common filenames. A list was created with these filenames, which later deployed to find associations with the filenames in the URLs of the network activity.
- U.5 Port number in the URL: Researchers stated that benign web servers often use the standard port 80, whilst the malicious ones mostly deploy other ports [36]. Thus, we search for different port numbers than the standard ones (80, 443) in the URLs of the network activity.
- U.6 Maximum number of occurrences of the “+” character in the URL: The plus symbol indicates that there is a whitespace in the URL. We count the occurrences of this character in the URLs and as a feature we extract the maximum number.
- U.7 Maximum number of occurrences of the “&” character in the URL: The URLs to deploy multiple parameters utilize the ampersand character. We count the occurrences of this character in each URL of the network activity, and as a feature we deploy the maximum number.
- U.8 Maximum number of occurrences of the “-” character in the URL: Many URLs contain the dash character, however, the malicious ones, since they are more complicated, usually comprise more dashes than the benign ones. We calculate the number of dashes in each URL of the network activity, and as a feature we utilized the maximum number.
- U.9 Maximum number of occurrences of the “/” character in the URL: The slash character, when used in the URL of an HTTP request, depicts the requested path to the server. Usually, malicious web pages host malicious files in deep paths. We keep track of the number of occurrences of this character in each URL of the network activity, and as a feature, we deploy the maximum number.
- U.10 Jar file: Instead of the application/java-archive header, we also record whether a jar file is presented in a URL. This feature is employed in the EK infection step 4 of Figure 1.
- U.11 Jnlp file: JNLP (Java Network Launching Protocol) contains information such as the remote address to download a jar file and it is used to launch and manage Java programs on the web. To this end, the presence of a jnlp file is also extracted from the URLs.
- U.12 Swf file: The swf (ShockWave) file is an animation created with Adobe Flash and can be played by a browser that has the Flash plugin installed. In addition to the application/x-shockwave-flash header we search in the network activity for URLs that contain swf files. This feature is deployed in the EK infection step 4 as presented in Figure 1.
- U.13 Exe file: EKs mostly target Windows systems and the majority of them deliver malwares in the form of exe files. Thus, this feature is used in the EK infection step 6 as presented in Figure 1.
- U.14 Xml file: The xml files have been used by EKs for exploitation purposes, thus it is considered as a feature.
- U.15 Mp4a-latm file: EKs utilized latm files, which are associated with audio data, to deliver the malware.
 - D.1 WWW subdomain in the URL: Malicious web pages usually do not specify a subdomain name [33]. We observed that various EKs follow this trend.
 - D.2 Subdomain: Malicious actors usually deploy subdomains to perform malicious actions. Thus, as a feature, we extract the presence of subdomains in network activity.
 - D.3 Suspicious TLD: We created a list of the most known Top-Level Domains (TLDs) for malicious activity, based on [37]. This list is later deployed to identify TLDs related with malicious activity in the network activity and we extracted it as a feature.
 - D.4 Domain/subdomain entropy: Bigger and more complex domain names appear to have higher entropy than smaller and simpler ones. Entropy is an efficient way to identify domains that have been algorithmically generated (e.g., DGA) and includes arbitrary characters [19] or domains that append dictionary words. EKs usually contain domains with high entropy.
 - D.5 Domain/subdomain with uncorrelated words: EK’s domains use randomly generated domains by appending different words from a dictionary to seem more benign from domains that are algorithmically generated. In this case, the formed domain name consists of words that have no relation to each other. We extracted whether the network activity comprises this domain name form.
 - D.6 Domain/subdomain length: The domain name length is a feature that has been used before in various researches and has been proved to be effective. Hence, we calculate the domain and/or subdomain name lengths of the network activity and extract the maximum number.
 - D.7 Suspicious domain name: This feature keeps track of suspicious domain names. As a suspicious domain name, we define: (a) a domain name that is comprised of arbitrary characters that compose an unreadable string, and (b) a domain name that is registered in the list³.

Connection Features: This category includes features that describe the network activity related to the HTTP requests and responses. In this category, the features are represented by an integer and real number values.

- C.1 Number of HTTP GET requests: In this feature, we count the number of HTTP GET requests that appeared in the network activity.
- C.2 Number of HTTP POST requests: Similar to the previous feature, we extract also the HTTP POST requests.
- C.3 The average length of HTTP response: We calculate the average number of HTTP responses in the network activity and extract it as a feature.

All the features that were discussed in this section along with their value type are presented in Table 1.

³www.malwaredomainlist.com

Table 1: Extracted Features (the bold font indicates the most valuable features based on feature selection)

Feature category	#	Feature name	Type	Description
Header Features	H.CT.1	Content-Type: text/html	Binary	Presence of text/html header
	H.CT.2	Content-Type: application/java-archive	Binary	Presence of application/java-archive
	H.CT.3	Content-Type: application/javascript	Binary	Presence of application/javascript
	H.CT.4	Content-Type: application/java-applet	Binary	Presence of application/java-applet
	H.CT.5	Content-Type: application/octet-stream	Binary	Presence of application/octet-stream
	H.CT.6	Content-Type: application/xml	Binary	Presence of application/xml
	H.CT.7	Content-Type: application/x-shockwave-flash	Binary	Presence of application/x-shockwave-flash
	H.CT.8	Content-Type: application/x-silverlight-app	Binary	Presence of application/x-silverlight-app
	H.CT.9	Content-Type: application/postscript	Binary	Presence of application/postscript
	H.CT.10	Content-Type: application/pdf	Binary	Presence of application/pdf
	H.CT.11	Content-Type: application/x-msdownload	Binary	Presence of application/x-msdownload
	H.CT.12	Content-Type: application/x-msdos-program	Binary	Presence of application/x-msdos-program
	H.CT.13	Content-Type: application/x-dosexec	Binary	Presence of application/x-dosexec
	H.UA	User-Agent	Binary	Absence of User-Agent header
H.CD	Content-Disposition: attachment	Binary	Presence of Content-Disposition: attachment header	
H.CE	Content-Encoding	Binary	Presence of Content-Encoding header	
Redirection Features	R.1	HTTP Redirection	Binary	Presence of HTTP 3XX code
	R.2	Location Header	Binary	Presence of Location header
	R.3	Referrer Header	Binary	Presence of Referrer header
	R.4	URL Parameter Redirection	Binary	Presence of URL parameter that contain an external URL
Evasion Features	E.1	JavaScript Obfuscation	Binary	Presence of obfuscated JavaScript code
	E.2	HTML Obfuscation	Binary	Presence of obfuscated HTML code
URL & Domain Features	U.1	Max URL length	Integer	Maximum URL length
	U.2	Max URI directory depth	Integer	Maximum URI directory depth
	U.3	IP address in the URL	Binary	Presence of an IP address
	U.4	Suspicious filename in the URL	Binary	Presence of a suspicious filename
	U.5	Port number in the URL	Binary	Presence of a port number
	U.6	Max no. of "+" in the URL	Integer	Max no. of occurrences of the "+" in the URLs
	U.7	Max no. of "&" in the URL	Integer	Max no. of occurrences of the "&" in the URLs
	U.8	Max no. of "." in the URL	Integer	Max no. of occurrences of the "." in the URLs
	U.9	Max no. of "/" in the URL	Integer	Max no. of occurrences of the "/" in the URLs
	U.10	Jar file in the URL	Binary	Presence of a .jar in the URL
	U.11	Jnlp file in the URL	Binary	Presence of .jnlp in the URL
	U.12	Swf file in the URL	Binary	Presence of .swf in the URL
	U.13	Exe file in the URL	Binary	Presence of .exe in the URL
	U.14	Xml file in the URL	Binary	Presence of .xml in the URL
	U.15	Mp4a-latm file in the URL	Binary	Presence of .latm in the URL
	D.1	WWW subdomain in the URL	Binary	Absence of the WWW subdomain
	D.2	Subdomain	Binary	Presence of subdomain
D.3	Suspicious TLD	Binary	Presence of suspicious TLD (based on the list) in the URL	
D.4	Domain/Subdomain entropy	Real	Max entropy of domain/subdomain	
D.5	Domain/subdomain with uncorrelated words	Binary	Presence of domain/subdomain with uncorrelated words	
D.6	Domain/subdomain length	Integer	The max length of domains/subdomain	
D.7	Suspicious domain name	Binary	Presence of a suspicious domain name	
Connection Features	C.1	Number of HTTP GET method	Integer	The number of GET requests that appear in the network activity
	C.2	The number of HTTP POST method	Integer	The number of POST requests that appear in the network activity
	C.3	The average length of HTTP response	Real	The average length of the HTTP response in the network activity

5. EKnad

EKnad proposes an ML-based detection methodology as depicted in Figure 2. This methodology contains two phases: i) the *pre-processing* phase that contains two steps, the *HTTP Traffic Extraction* and the *creation of potential EK sessions*, and, ii) the *EK detection* phase that comprises three steps: *feature extraction*, *feature selection*, and *classification*. Next, the details of each phase and steps are elaborated.

5.1. Pre-processing

5.1.1. HTTP Traffic Extraction

The *HTTP traffic extraction* is the process that extracts only the information related to the HTTP protocol from the PCAP file since the rest of the protocols do not provide any valuable information to facilitate EK detection. For example, the DNS protocol is removed because domains are not used by EKs, since typically they redirect directly to IP addresses. In this step, all the HTTP flows (i.e., HTTP requests and response packets) are extracted and saved in separate text files. By discarding unnecessary information from the rest of the protocols, we reduce the classifiers' training time. The HTTP traffic was

Figure 2: EKnad's detection procedure

extracted by implementing a Python code that automatically identifies the HTTP protocol inside PCAP files.

5.1.2. Creation of Potential EK Sessions

Modern websites often link to dozens of sites from a single site, so the number of web pages accessed from a web browser ranges from thousands to tens of thousands. This means that the number of HTTP flows to be checked are very large and,

thus, it is difficult to analyze them directly. For this reason, we group all the HTTP requests and responses of an HTTP session from a specific domain and all the redirection chains that were generated by this domain (if any) as one single session named *Potential EK session*. A potential EK session resembles an HTTP (or Web) session, but the former captures the network traffic of an attack pattern of an EK as we analyzed in Section 2.1, while the latter is the network traffic generated by a particular TCP connection established for example when visiting a website in the Internet. The rationale behind this grouping is to isolate potentially malicious EK traffic and extract features on the basis of each potential EK session. In this way, the HTTP traffic is divided into smaller parts to improve the detection accuracy and noise coming from lower network layers which are all captured in a packet trace (e.g., IP layer headers, layer 2, etc) is removed.

Algorithm 1 depicts the process of generating potential EK sessions. The input of the algorithm is the HTTP traffic that has been extracted from the network traffic in the previous step (i.e., HTTP Traffic Extraction) and the output is a set of potential EK sessions. The main functions of the algorithm are the identification and extraction of: (1) the traffic that is generated by a specific domain and (2) the redirects that have been occurred. The identification of the HTTP traffic of a specific domain is achieved by inspecting the *Host HTTP header* (starting from the first domain that appears in the HTTP traffic) of successive HTTP requests in a loop, which ends when a new domain name (or IP address) appears in the HTTP traffic (lines 22-33). Furthermore, the HTTP requests that do not have a response are discarded. Particularly, when a new request is processed, algorithm 1 checks whether this request has a response (lines 8-12 and 26-32). In case that there is no response, the potential EK session ends, and the algorithm proceeds to the next request. The redirects are discovered in 4 ways: a) by comparing the domain in the *Referer HTTP header* with the domain of the host of the previous HTTP request (lines 37-39), b) by comparing the domain of the *Host HTTP header* with the domain of the *Location HTTP header* of the previous HTTP response (lines 40-42), c) by checking whether the code of the HTTP response refers to a redirect code (e.g., 300, 301, 302, etc.) and concurrently whether the *Location HTTP header* of the response contains the same domain as the host of the previous request (lines 43-45), and d) by checking if the domain of the *Host HTTP header* appears in the body of the previous HTTP response, to capture cases such as redirects via iframes (lines 46-48). In case that there are no further redirects, the potential EK session is finalized (lines 49-51), and the algorithm continues with the next visited domain in the HTTP traffic. The process is repeated until there are no other domains in the HTTP traffic.

Algorithm 1 has been designed to be deployed into individual hosts. In order to operate at a network level, the HTTP traffic should be captured at the entry of (sub)networks. In this case, algorithm 1 should first separate the network traffic based on the IP addresses of the individual hosts and then create potential EK sessions for each host. Capturing the HTTP traffic of a (sub)network requires either a special hardware device namely Network Test Access Point (TAP) or a router with a

Algorithm 1: Generating Potential EK sessions

```

1  Input HTTP Traffic;
2  counterA ← 0;
3  counterB ← 0;
4  counterC ← 0;
5  redirectCode ← {300, 301, 302, 303, 304, 307, 308};
6  hostHeader[counterA] ← domain_host_header;
7  potential_EK_session[counterB] ← http_request;
8  if http_response is EMPTY then
9    | exit;
10 else
11   | potential_EK_session[counterB+1] ← http_response;
12 end
13 startSession ← True;
14 while startSession = True do
15   Continue to next HTTP Request;
16   if http_response is EMPTY then
17     | exit;
18   else
19     counterA ← counterA+1;
20     counterB ← counterB+2;
21     hostHeader[counterA] ← domain_host_header;
22     while hostHeader[counterA] = hostHeader[counterA-1] do
23       potential_EK_session[counterB] ← http_request;
24       potential_EK_session[counterB+1] ← http_response;
25       Continue to next HTTP Request;
26       if http_response is EMPTY then
27         | exit;
28       else
29         counterA ← counterA+1;
30         counterB ← counterB+2;
31         hostHeader[counterA] ← domain_host_header;
32       end
33     end
34     refererHeader ← domain_referer_header;
35     responseCode ← http_response.code;
36     locationHeader[counterC] ← domain_location_header;
37     if refererHeader = hostHeader[counterA-1] then
38       potential_EK_session[counterB] ← http_request;
39       potential_EK_session[counterB+1] ← http_response;
40     else if hostHeader[counterA] = locationHeader[counterC-1] then
41       potential_EK_session[counterB] ← http_request;
42       potential_EK_session[counterB+1] ← http_response;
43     else if responseCode = redirectCode AND locationHeader[counterC] = hostHeader[counterA]
44       then
45       potential_EK_session[counterB] ← http_request;
46       potential_EK_session[counterB+1] ← http_response;
47     else if hostHeader[counterA] in http_response.body[counterA-1] then
48       potential_EK_session[counterB] ← http_request;
49       potential_EK_session[counterB+1] ← http_response;
50     else
51       startSession ← FALSE;
52     end
53   end
54   counterC ← counterC+1;
55 end
56 Output Potential EK sessions;

```

SPAN port to mirror the traffic. In general, we argue that the deployment of algorithm 1 into a larger network depends on the considered network architecture.

5.2. Exploit Kit Detection

5.2.1. Feature Extraction

As its name implies, the feature extraction step in EKnad extracts the features from the potential EK sessions along with their numerical values. To this end, we built a joint set F that contains all the observable feature categories of the taxonomy:

$$F = F_{\text{Header}} \cup F_{\text{Redirection}} \cup F_{\text{Evasion}} \cup F_{\text{URL\&Domain}} \cup F_{\text{Connection}}$$

The feature taxonomy that comprised the feature set F is:

$$F_{\text{Header}} = \{F_{H,CT.1}, F_{H,CT.2}, \dots, F_{H,CT.19}, F_{H,UA}, F_{H,CD}, F_{H,CE}\}$$

$$F_{\text{Redirection}} = \{F_{R.1}, F_{R.2}, F_{R.3}, F_{R.4}\}$$

$$F_{\text{Evasion}} = \{F_{E.1}, F_{E.2}\}$$

$$F_{\text{URL\&Domain}} = \{F_{UD.1}, F_{UD.2}, \dots, F_{UD.22}\}$$

$$F_{\text{Connection}} = \{F_{C.1}, F_{C.2}, F_{C.3}\}$$

Utilizing the set F , we define an $|F|$ -dimensional vector space that is represented by binary values, integers, and real numbers. Particularly, 36 features are represented by binary values, nine features are integer numbers, and two features are real numbers. The value of each feature is shown in Table 1. Of note, the features were extracted from the HTTP traffic by implementing a

Python program, which takes as input the traffic of the potential EK sessions and generates a Comma-Separated Value (CSV) file that contains the values of the features.

5.2.2. Feature Selection

Feature Selection is an essential data processing step to identify the most important features prior to applying an ML algorithm. Its objective is to remove irrelevant or redundant features without much loss of information. The advantage of Feature Selection is three-fold: a) To achieve faster training of the algorithm by reducing the number of features, b) to avoid overfitting the algorithm by deploying only the required features, and c) to attain better prediction results (i.e., improve the classification accuracy) by employing only the most informative features. The Feature Selection methods can be broadly grouped into four categories, named filter, wrapper, embedded, and hybrid methods [38]. The filter method evaluates the features according to heuristics based on general characteristics of the training data, without relying on any learning algorithm. In contrast, the wrapper, embedded, and hybrid methods require a learning algorithm and rely on its performance to determine the effectiveness of the features. To this end, the latter methods are insufficient for EKnad, as they contradict the generalization scope of the proposed methodology. Hence, to identify the most relevant features of EKs' HTTP activity, we employed a filter-based method. We chose the Information Gain (IG) feature selection technique [39] as it has been proved to be very efficient in EK detection field [27], [34].

The IG (or entropy) is calculated for each feature for the output variable, which in our case is the class that the network activity belongs to, namely EK or benign. The IG is defined as the reduction in the uncertainty about the class C of an item having the feature F . The uncertainty is measured in entropy and for C is defined as:

$$H(C) = - \sum P(c_i) \log_2(P(c_i)) \quad (1)$$

where $P(c_i)$ is the prior probabilities for all values of C . The uncertainty for C after observing F is determined by the conditional entropy defined as:

$$H(C|F) = - \sum_j P(f_j) \sum_i P(c_i|f_j) \log_2(P(c_i|f_j)) \quad (2)$$

where $P(c_i|f_j)$ is the posterior probabilities of C given the values of F . The IG of a feature F with respect to the class C , is its mutual information with respect to C and is defined as:

$$IG(C|F) = H(C) - H(C|F) \quad (3)$$

Respectfully to the IG, it is clear that a feature F is considered more correlated to class C than feature X , if $IG(C|F) > IG(C|X)$. The feature ranking can be calculated by equation (3). Using the equation (3) we calculated the IG value for each feature and ranked them based on their values in descending order. The IG values ranged between 0.3135 and 0.00014. Next, we performed multiple experiments with different selection of features based on their IG values. Specifically, we selected: i) features with above 0.2 IG value (5 features in total), ii) features with above 0.1 IG value (9 features in total), iii) features with above 0.04 IG value (14 features), iv) features with above 0.02

IG value (20 features), v) features with above 0.01 IG value (26 features), and vi) features with an IG value above 0.00014 (all 47 features). For all ML algorithms except MLP, the best detection results were achieved when we selected the features with above 0.02 IG value, which were 20 in total. The results of the MLP algorithm were not affected significantly and the same detection performance was achieved when used 20, 26, and 47 features. Thus, in order to attain the best performance with the minimum overhead, we selected 20 features. The selected features are presented with bold font in Table 1.

5.2.3. Classification

The classification step is the crux of the proposed methodology. It is a binary classification task, where the deployed EK samples were acquired from publicly available sources (e.g., [26]), namely the class of the EK samples is already known. For this reason, we have utilized supervised learning, while unsupervised learning is more appropriate for clustering unlabeled data (i.e., grouping the data based on similarities or differences without prior knowledge of their class) [40]. Furthermore, during the evaluation process, we tested a DL approach, where the MLP ANN was applied with various hidden layers (i.e., 1, 2, 3, and 4). However, the performance improvement with more than two hidden layers was not significant, hence, there was no need for employing a DL approach. In supervised learning, in the learning/training phase, there are input variables x and output variables Y and the deployed algorithm learns the mapping function f to predict the output based on the input $Y = f(x)$. In this research, the input x of the supervised learning refers to the network activity (i.e., the HTTP traffic), and the output Y depicts the class of the network activity (EK or benign).

A challenge of this research is to identify the most appropriate ML algorithms to classify network traffic to EK or benign. To this end, we considered several supervised ML classifiers from various categories: 1) the ensemble learning Random Forest (RF) [41], 2) the probability-based Bayesian Network (BN) [42], 3) the rule-based Decision Table (DT) [43], 4) the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) [44], 5) the instance-based k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) [45], and 6) the tree-based J48 [46]. The aforementioned algorithms that have been extensively utilized in the malware detection field for classification purposes [47], [48] and they will be also deployed in the classification step of EKnad. The classification is divided into two phases; (1) the training phase before application, where the algorithm is trained on a dataset, and (2) the testing phase, where the model is applied to unknown data (data that has not been used in the training phase) to make predictions. An essential task of the learning phase is hyperparameter tuning. Hyperparameters are the parameters of the algorithms that are deployed to control the learning process. In this research, the estimation of the hyperparameters' values is performed via manual tuning. The latter may require more effort, but it facilitates the understanding of the behavior of each algorithm and how the alterations of the hyperparameters affect the learning phase of the algorithm.

6. EKnad Evaluation and Discussion

6.1. Methodology

To thoroughly and correctly assess the detection capabilities of EKnad, we considered state-of-the-art methodologies and guidelines for evaluating ML algorithms in the computer security domain [49]. More specifically, there is a significant body of works (e.g., [50], [51], [52]) that have identified pitfalls in the evaluation procedure of ML algorithms when they are applied to detect malware, spam and network attacks. We have identified that the same erroneous evaluation methodologies have been also carried out in previous works related to EK detection, undermining the trustworthiness of their obtained experimental results.

In the following, we present the most relevant rules that should be followed for evaluating the performance of an EK classifier, in order to avoid introducing bias and attain misleading results.

- A1: In real world scenarios, malware is encountered much less frequently to goodware. Accordingly, the testing dataset must reflect this observation and utilize a realistic malware-to-goodware ratio [50]. In our case, EKs are the minority class, while the benign traffic is the majority class. Thus, an imbalanced dataset must be used in which the EKs samples are far less than the benign traffic. Violation of this rule, means that balanced datasets are used and numerical results may be inflated. A previous work that has not considered this rule is [15] that utilized a testing dataset with 9,362 EKs and 10,541 benign samples, which accounts for almost 50% EK and 50% benign samples.
- A2: Samples from the same malware family should not be used in both training and testing steps. As malware samples from the same family bear similarities, it becomes evident that violating this rule may boost the performance of the classifier. This rule is violated when the evaluation of the classifiers is based only on the K-fold cross-validation, since the latter uses all the available samples for both training and testing. This rule applies also in EK detection, since various EKs have enough “code and functionality overlap” to be considered as part of the same family. Many past papers for EK detection do not take into account this rule. For example, the work in [23] utilize only K-fold cross-validation to estimate the accuracy of the EK detection classifier.
- A3: The training dataset must be temporally precedent to the testing ones. Otherwise, results may be inflated by including future knowledge in the classifier. An example of a past work in the field of EK detection that violates this rule is [27].
- A4: The ML based detection system must be evaluated using more than one classifier. Although this may seem evident, there are some works for EK detection such as [14] that consider only one classification algorithm to obtain results.
- A5: Benign and malware samples should not correspond to different time periods [50]. Otherwise, the classifier

may learn to distinguish applications from different time periods, due to feature differences coming from time decay leading to artificially high performance. For instance, old malware samples may use an old (or even deprecated) version of an API and new benign samples may use an updated version of the API with different parameters or naming. The updated API may be sufficient for the classifier to distinguish malware from benign samples. We were not able to identify past works in EK detection that violate this rule, not because they take into account this rule, but mainly due to incomplete or vague information provided regarding their experiments.

From the above rules, EKnad readily complies with **Rule A4** and with **Rule A5**. More specifically, as we mentioned in Section 5.2.3, EKnad will utilize not one but six different classifiers to select the most efficient one (i.e., RF, BN, DT, KNN, J48, and MLP). Regarding **Rule A5**, EKnad is based on stable HTTP features (i.e., HTTP headers), which have not been modified over the years. Therefore, we argue that EKnad is not affected by the different time periods that the benign and EK traffic has been collected. In the next section, we discuss how we created our datasets and orchestrated our experiments to abide by the remaining rules (i.e., A1-A3).

6.2. Datasets and Experiments

We collected the EK network activity files (in PCAP file format) from the malware-traffic-analysis.net [26] website, which contains several EK PCAP files from 2013 until the time of writing this paper (2021). We downloaded all PCAP files from this website (more than 850) and we performed a preliminary analysis in order to remove PCAP files that included the same EK. As such, we ended up with 114 unique EK samples (i.e., PCAP files) from 2013 to 2020. The collected EK files belong to 26 different EK families, including well-known EKs such as Angler, Rig, Blackhole, Neutrino, Nuclear, Magnitude, etc. The utilized EK network traffic covers all the state-of-the-art exploits and malwares that EKs have used over the years 2013-2020. Particularly, the EK samples exploit several vulnerabilities, for instance, CVE-2017-8570, CVE-2017-0143, CVE-2018-11776, CVE-2016-4117, CVE-2018-4878, and CVE-2020-0674. The majority of these vulnerabilities belong to the Internet Explorer, Microsoft Edge, Mozilla Firefox, and Google Chrome browsers; Adobe Flash and Silverlight plugins. Furthermore, the EK samples contain the network traffic of the malware delivery process from various malware families, such as RATs (njRAT, Quasar, Gh0st, etc.), Trojans (Smokeloader, Andromeda, AZORult, Zeus, etc.), Botnets (Mirai, Zbot, Dnabot, etc.), Ransomwares (Eris, Maze, CryptoWall, Magniber, etc.), and Coinminers. Hence, the collected dataset provides a thorough depiction of the EK activity in the wild. Regarding the benign samples, to the best of our knowledge there are no public datasets of benign network traffic, thus, we acquired the benign network traffic from the laboratory of the University of Piraeus. The traffic was captured during the period December 2020 to January 2021 using Wireshark⁴. The network traffic

⁴<https://www.wireshark.org/>

originated from ten different desktop computers and resulted in 468 PCAP files. Next, these PCAP files were parsed on the VirusTotal API⁵ to check whether they will be flagged by AV products. From this test, 24 PCAP files were excluded leaving in total 444 benign network traffic files.

The EK and benign samples were combined to build five distinct datasets named: i) *all-EK* dataset, ii) *old-EK* dataset, iii) *new-EK* dataset, iv) *popular-EK* dataset, and v) *unknown-EK* dataset. To abide by **Rule A1** (i.e., the EK network traffic should be much less than the benign), the ratio between EK and benign samples is approximately 25% in all datasets. The *popular-EK* dataset is comprised by 65 EK samples from the most well-known EK families (RIG, Neutrino, Blackhole, Magnitude, Angler, and Nuclear) and 249 randomly selected benign samples, while the *unknown-EK* dataset includes 49 EK samples from the remaining 20 EK families that are less known and 195 randomly selected benign samples. The *old-EK* dataset is comprised of EK samples collected from the years 2013-2016, which contains 74 EK samples from 21 EK families, and 286 randomly selected benign samples. The *new-EK* dataset is comprised of EK samples from the years 2017-2020, which contains 40 EKs from 9 EK families and 158 randomly selected benign samples. The *all-EK* contains all the EK and benign samples, namely 114 EK and 444 benign samples. We note that we deployed classifiers without focusing on techniques particularly designed for imbalanced data, since our objective is not to address the data imbalance issue, but to validate the detection capabilities of EKnad.

To thoroughly evaluate EKnad we performed four distinct experiments. In experiment 1, we tested whether EKnad can detect less-known EK families, when it is trained on well-known EK families. As such, we deployed the *popular-EK* dataset for training the classifiers and the *unknown-EK* dataset for testing them. In this way, we guarantee the fact that the same EK family will not be deployed in both training and testing phases (compliance with **Rule A2**). In experiment 2, we investigated if EKnad can detect state-of-the-art EKs, when trained on a dataset of older EKs. Particularly, the EK samples has been separated based on the chronological capturing of the EK network traffic. The rationale here is that new EK is not used for the training of the classifiers; instead training is based exclusively on old EKs, while testing is based on new EKs (compliance with **Rule A3**). As such we utilized the *old-EK* dataset for training the classifiers and the *new-EK* dataset for testing them. In the experiment 3, we deployed K-fold cross-validation in the *all-EK* dataset. Although the K-fold cross-validation is not sufficient enough to accurately depict the models performance (see Section 6.1 - Rule A2), it is one of the most common evaluation methods of classifiers in the literature. Thus, experiment 3 complements the first two experiments and allows us to have a holistic view of EKnad’s efficacy. Finally, in experiment 4, we compared the detection rate of EKnad with two prominent open-source IDS named Snort (version 2.9)⁶ and Suricata (ver-

Table 2: Number of EK samples per family

#	EK	#Samples	#	EK	#Samples
1	Neutrino	6	14	Zuponcic	1
2	DotkaChef	2	15	FlashPack	4
3	Cool	1	16	Goon/Infinity	4
4	Terror	3	17	Nebula	1
5	g01pack	1	18	Nuclear	6
6	Blackhole	2	19	Angler	6
7	GrandSoft	2	20	Magnitude	6
8	SweetOrange	3	21	Fiesta	8
9	Sibhost	1	22	Rig	39
10	Gondad	1	23	KaiXin	4
11	Whitehole	1	24	Spelevo	6
12	Sundown	4	25	Fallout	1
13	Styx	1	26	Lord	1
			Total		114

sion 5.0.3)⁷ using the *old-EK* and the *new-EK* datasets. We would like also to reiterate the fact that all experiments comply with **Rule A4**, since we utilize multiple classifiers for the evaluation of EKnad and also with **Rule A5**, since we do not utilize any time-affected feature (see Section 4) that would help the classifiers to distinguish EK traffic from benign traffic. To facilitate researchers reproduce our results and compare EKnad with future solutions we publicly share the deployed datasets [53].

6.3. Metrics

As described in the above subsection, our benchmark data is imbalanced in the sense that the number of EK samples is much less than the number of benign traffic (25% EK over benign samples). So the traditional accuracy measure is not reliable for evaluating the algorithm performance. Following the previous studies in validating the algorithms for imbalanced data [54], [55], we have selected several performance metrics in addition to AUC and accuracy to evaluate our experiments. In particular, the comparison of RF, BN, DT, MLP, KNN, and J48 classifiers were based on the following metrics:

- **True Positive Rate (TPR) or Recall:** Depicts the correctly classified EK files compared with the total number of EK files:

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4)$$

- **False Positive Rate (FPR):** Presents the mistakenly classified benign files compared with the total number of benign files:

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{FP + TN} \quad (5)$$

- **Precision:** Depicts the correctly EK files compared with the total number of files that classified as EK:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (6)$$

- **Accuracy:** Percentage of correctly classified files compared with the total number of files:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (7)$$

⁵<https://www.virustotal.com/gui/>

⁶<https://www.snort.org/>

⁷<https://suricata-ids.org/>

- *F1-Score*: A metric to measure the accuracy, which considers both the *precision* and *recall*. It presents a better measure in case of class imbalanced (e.g., when the malicious samples are fewer than benign).

$$F1 - Score = 2 \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + \frac{1}{2}(FP + FN)} \quad (8)$$

- *Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC)*: Is a metric to measure binary classifications that is less influenced by class imbalance, since it considers the accuracies and error rates on both classes [55]. The higher the correlation between “true” and predicted values, the better the prediction.

$$MCC = \frac{TP * TN - FP * FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}} \quad (9)$$

- *Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC)*: Provides an aggregate measure of a classifier’s ability to distinguish between classes.

$$AUC = \frac{\sum_{n \in N} \sum_{p \in P} 1[f(n) < f(p)]}{|N||P|} \quad (10)$$

where $|N|$ is the number of EK samples in the dataset, $|P|$ is the number of benign samples in the dataset and $1[f(n) < f(p)]$ denotes an indicator function that returns 1 if $f(n) < f(p)$ is true, otherwise it returns 0 [56].

- *True Positive (TP)*: Number of correctly classified EK network traffic files.
- *False Positive (FP)*: Number of mistakenly classified benign network traffic files.
- *True Negative (TN)*: Number of correctly classified benign network traffic files.
- *False Negative (FN)*: Number of mistakenly classified EK network traffic files.

Finally, we define the *Detection Rate (DR)* as the number of successfully detected EKs divided by the number of all tested EKs. This metric will be used only in experiment 4.

6.4. Evaluation Results

We ran the experiments on Linux Ubuntu 18.04 64-bit with 8GB RAM and Intel Core i5-9400F 2.9GHZ. The WEKA 3.9.5 ML framework [57] was deployed to build the ML classifiers and obtain results.

6.4.1. First Experiment: EK family separation

The goal of this experiment is two-fold. First, to deploy different EK families in the training phase of EKnad than in the testing. Second, to assess whether EKnad can detect less-known EKs, when it is trained on well-known EKs (for which there are more available sources). The EK samples were separated based on the EK family they belong (see Section 6.2). That is, the *popular-EK* dataset contains EKs from the dominant EK families RIG, Neutrino, Blackhole, Magnitude, Angler, and Nuclear and it was used to train the classifiers, while the *unknown-EK* dataset is comprised by 20 EK families that are less-known and it was used for testing the classifiers. Furthermore, the datasets are imbalanced (25% EK over benign samples) to represent a realistic scenario.

The results of the first experiment are shown in Table 3. MLP yielded the best performance, since it misclassified only

Table 3: Results of experiment 1

Model	Recall	FPR	Precision	Accuracy	F1-Score	MCC	AUC
RF	0.959	0.133	0.959	0.959	0.958	0.869	0.98
BN	0.951	0.18	0.952	0.95	0.949	0.842	0.994
DT	0.898	0.301	0.893	0.897	0.892	0.659	0.908
MLP	0.984	0.065	0.984	0.983	0.983	0.949	0.996
KNN	0.955	0.179	0.957	0.954	0.953	0.857	0.891
J48	0.918	0.28	0.918	0.918	0.913	0.729	0.928

four FNs, which led to 0.983 accuracy, 0.065 FPR, 0.983 F1-Score, and 0.949 MCC. RF misclassified eight FNs and two FPs resulted in 0.959 accuracy, 0.133 FPR, 0.869 MCC, and 0.958 F1-Score, while KNN misclassified eleven FNs achieving 0.954 accuracy, 0.179 FPR, 0.953 F1-Score, and 0.857 MCC. BN also attained comparable results, namely 0.95 accuracy, 0.18 FPR, and 0.949 F1-Score, and 0.842 MCC. J48 and DT accomplished the worst results, misclassifying seventeen and eighteen FNs, as well as three and one FPs respectively. J48 attained 0.918 accuracy, 0.28 FPR, 0.913 F1-Score, and 0.729 MCC while DT achieved 0.897 accuracy, 0.301 FPR, 0.892 F1-Score, and 0.659 MCC. Overall, the best and worst recall, precision, and AUC values were attained by MLP and DT respectively.

The misclassifications of the EK samples are caused because some EKs of the popular-EK dataset, which was utilized for training, deploy different techniques for the exploitation and the malware delivery than the EKs in the unknown-EK dataset that was used for testing. Thus, the values of some features of these two datasets differ. More specifically, the features Content-Type: application/octet-stream and Content-Type: application/java-archive mostly appear in popular-EK datasets, while the features Content-Type: application/x-shockwave-flash and Content-Type: application/x-msdownload mostly appear in the unknown-EK dataset leading to the erroneous classification of some EK samples.

Regarding the misclassifications of the benign samples, it occurred in samples that have similar features with the EKs. Particularly, the features: Jar file in the URL, Suspicious filename in the URL, high Domain/Subdomain Entropy, Content-Type: application/octet-stream, and Content-Encoding appear both in EK and benign samples. Hence the classifiers could not distinguish the benign network activity from the EK. These misclassifications are difficult to be solved, because even though we have deployed a thorough feature set that considers the whole infection procedure of EKs, there are subtle differences between well-known and unknown EK families that the ML algorithms cannot identify.

6.4.2. Second Experiment: Chronological separation of EK samples

The goal of the second experiment is to test the detection performance of EKnad on newer EKs, when it is trained on older EKs. As we mentioned in Section 6.2, the EK samples were separated chronologically on two datasets, where the *old-EK* dataset contains EKs from 2013-2016 and it was used as a training dataset of the classifiers, while the *new-EK* dataset is comprised by newer EKs from 2017-2020 and it was used for testing the classifiers. As previously, the datasets are imbalanced (25% EKs over benign) to represent a realistic scenario.

Table 4 illustrates the results of the second experiment. As

Table 4: Results of experiment 2

Model	Recall	FPR	Precision	Accuracy	F1-Score	MCC	AUC
RF	0.98	0.08	0.98	0.979	0.979	0.937	0.98
BN	0.98	0.08	0.98	0.979	0.979	0.937	0.98
DT	0.919	0.245	0.917	0.919	0.916	0.736	0.97
MLP	0.99	0.04	0.99	0.989	0.99	0.969	0.997
KNN	0.97	0.12	0.971	0.969	0.969	0.905	0.925
J48	0.949	0.162	0.949	0.949	0.948	0.838	0.896

in the first experiment, the MLP achieved the best detection performance, namely 0.989 accuracy, 0.04 FPR, 0.99 F1-Score, and 0.969 MCC, which was the result of only two FNs. Following, RF and BN had the same performance. Particularly, they both attained 0.979 accuracy, 0.08 FPR 0.979 F1-Score, and 0.937 MCC, due to the erroneous classification of 4 FNs. KNN misclassified in total six FNs and attained 0.969 accuracy, 0.12 FPR, 0.969 F1-Score, and 0.905 MCC, while J48 yielded 0.949 accuracy, 0.162 FPR, 0.948 F1-Score, and 0.838 MCC, since it misclassified eight FNs and two FPs. DT attained the worst results in this experiment, as it misclassified twelve FNs and four FPs caused 0.919 accuracy, 0.245 FPR, 0.916 F1-Score, and 0.736 MCC. Overall, MLP had the best recall (0.99), precision (0.99), and AUC (0.999), while the worst recall (0.919), precision (0.917), and AUC (0.97) attained by DT.

Elaborating more on the misclassifications, when it comes to the EK traffic, several differences can be found between the EK traffic of older (i.e., the training samples) and newer EKs (i.e., the testing samples), which are reflected on the features. For instance, the majority of older EKs utilized IP addresses instead of domain names, while newer EKs use Domain/Subdomain with uncorrelated words or Suspicious domain names. These differences are reflected in the URL & Domain features, which potentially caused the misclassifications of the EK samples. Regarding the misclassifications of the benign traffic, the reasons are similar with the previous experiment, namely the benign samples included features that appeared also in the EK samples (see section 6.4.1).

6.4.3. Third Experiment: 10-fold Cross-Validation

The third experiment aims on the evaluation of EKnad on all the EK samples (i.e., the *all-EK* dataset) using the K-fold cross validation with $K=10$. In K-fold cross-validation [58] the dataset D is randomly split into K mutually partitions (or folds) D_1, D_2, \dots, D_K of approximately equal size. Then, the algorithm is trained and tested K times, where each time a different fold of data is maintained for testing, and the remaining $K - 1$ folds are used for training. Every time the evaluation metrics were measured and then, a rotation takes place to change the fold that will be maintained for testing, and consequently, the remaining folds will be deployed for training. The K-fold cross-validation ends by calculating the mean value of all rotations for all the metrics. The advantage of this method is that all instances in the dataset are eventually used for both training and testing purposes.

The performance results of the 10-fold cross-validation on MLP, RF, BN, DT, KNN and J48 classifiers are depicted in Table 5. We observed once again that MLP outperformed all classifiers, since it accomplished 0.991 accuracy, 0.028 FPR, 0.991 F1-Score, 0.972 MCC. The results occurred after MLP mis-

Table 5: Results of experiment 3

Model	Recall	FPR	Precision	Accuracy	F1-Score	MCC	AUC
RF	0.989	0.042	0.989	0.989	0.989	0.967	0.999
BN	0.987	0.036	0.987	0.987	0.987	0.961	0.999
DT	0.955	0.064	0.957	0.955	0.956	0.867	0.976
MLP	0.991	0.028	0.991	0.991	0.991	0.972	0.999
KNN	0.984	0.063	0.984	0.983	0.984	0.95	0.965
J48	0.959	0.102	0.958	0.958	0.958	0.871	0.929

classified four FNs and one FP (benign classified as EK). Following, the RF classifier attained 0.989 accuracy, 0.042 FPR, 0.989 F1-score, 0.967 MCC, which was the result of the erroneous classification of six FNs. BN misclassified seven samples in total; five FNs and two FP, accomplishing 0.987 accuracy, 0.036 FPR, 0.987 F1-Score, 0.961 MCC. KNN attained 0.983 accuracy, 0.063 FPR, 0.984 F1-Score, 0.95 MCC, as a result of the misclassification of nine FNs. The tree-based classifier J48 misclassified fourteen FNs and nine FPs, achieving 0.958 accuracy, 0.102 FPR, 0.958 F1-Score, 0.871 MCC. Finally, DT accomplished slightly worst results in detection accuracy (0.955), F1-Score (0.956), and MCC (0.867) than J48, however, it accomplished better FPR (0.064). Particularly, it failed to classify eight FNs and seventeen FPs. Regarding the remaining evaluation metrics, MLP achieved the best results in recall (0.991) and precision (0.991), while DT yielded the worst results on recall (0.955) and precision (0.957). The MLP along with RF and BN achieved the best AUC value (0.999). J48 had the lowest AUC value (0.929), which was worst than DT (0.976) and KNN (0.965). We can assume that the misclassifications of the EK samples are caused because the network traffic of these EKs present similarities at a domain level with the benign traffic. That is, the values of some URL & Domain features, such as Domain/Subdomain Length, Domain/Subdomain entropy, Max no. of “-” in the URL, and Max no. of “/” in the URL, were close to benign samples.

6.4.4. Fourth Experiment: Comparison with Intrusion Detection Systems

The objective of the last experiment is to test whether EKnad is more efficient in the detection of EKs’ network traffic than two well-known rule-based IDS. In particular, we evaluated the DR and the FPR of Snort and Suricata IDS against EK network traffic and compared the results with EKnad using the MLP classifier (since it achieved the best results in the previous three experiments). The *old-EK* and the *new-EK* datasets were utilized to investigate whether the DR of the IDSs deteriorates on newer EKs. To compare the results of IDSs with EKnad, we deploy 10-fold cross-validation in the *old-EK* dataset to obtain numerical results, while we utilized the same numerical results of the previous experiment for the *new-EK* datasets.

It is evident that the detection performance of rule-based IDSs is directly related to the deployed rulesets. If the related rule for the detection of a specific EK sample is available, then the IDS will be able to detect and trigger an alarm. Snort and Suricata come with pre-installed rules, but these are limited and not sufficient to detect EKs. To this end, for Snort we utilized the EK rules from the latest subscribers rules (at the time of

Table 6: Results of experiment 4

Detection Method	DR old-EK	FPR old-EK	DR new-EK	FPR new-EK
EKnad (MLP)	98.64%	1%	97.5%	0.6%
Snort	87.83%	0.3%	80%	0.6%
Suricata	78.37%	0.3%	92.5%	0.6%

writing it was the snapshot_2983⁸). Regarding Suricata, we deployed the Proofpoint Emerging Threat (ET) open ruleset⁹. In this way, the deployed ruleset of Snort contained 751 EK rules, while the ruleset of Suricata was comprised of 1132 EK rules. It is important to mention that the ET open ruleset also provides rules for Snort; however, this ruleset was not deployed, because it did not contain a specific EK rule category. Before presenting the results of this experiment, it should be clarified that the tested IDSs were installed only with the obtained EK-specific rules to ensure that the IDSs will trigger an alarm only due to the detection of EK activity and not from other suspicious activities (e.g., half-open TCP connections, blacklisted URL domains, etc).

Results show that EKnad detected 72 out of 74 EKs in the old-EK dataset, accomplishing a 97.29% DR of the EK samples. Snort detected in total 65 EKs and its DR was 87.83%, while Suricata yielded worse results than Snort. Particularly, Suricata detected 58 EKs, which means a 78.37% DR. Moreover, in the new-EK dataset, EKnad detected 39 out of 40 EKs, accomplishing a 97.5% DR. In this dataset, Snort achieved worst results than Suricata. More specifically, Snort detected 32 out of 40 EKs, while Suricata detected 37 out of 40, namely Snort and Suricata reached 80% and 92.5% DR respectively. Regarding the FPR results, it is known that rule-based IDS typically have lower FPR than ML-based detection methods. In this experiment, Snort and Suricata attained the same FPR, namely 0.3% in the old-EK dataset and 0.6% in the new-EK dataset, due to the erroneous classification of only one benign sample in both datasets. On the other hand, EKnad misclassified three benign samples resulting in 1% FPR. However, in new-EK dataset it achieved the same FPR with Snort and Suricata, namely 0.3%. The results of this experiment are summarized in Table 6.

Elaborating more on the results, EKnad did not detect two EK samples from the category *old-EK* dataset and one from the *new-EK* dataset. In *old-EK* dataset, Snort did not detect 9 EKs samples from various EK families. Particularly, it did not detect: 1 out of 6 (1/6) Neutrino EKs, 2/4 Sundown EKs, 1/14 Rig EKs, 3/8 Fiesta EKs, 1/6 Magnitude EKs, and 1/1 Gondad EK. For the same dataset, Suricata did not detect 16 EKs samples: 3/3 Neutrino EKs, 1/4 Sundown EKs, 1/14 Rig EKs, 2/8 Fiesta EKs, 1/1 Gondad EK, 4/6 Angler EKs, 2/6 Nuclear EKs, 1/3 Flashpack EKs, and 1/3 SweetOrange EKs. In the *new-EK* dataset, Snort did not detect 8 EK: 6/24 Rig EKs, 1/1 Lord EK, and 1/1 Fallout EK; while Suricata did not detect 3 EKs, 1/1 Fallout EK, and 2/6 Spelevo EKs. As far as it concerns the potential reasons for the FP results of EKnad in the old-EK dataset, the benign samples, which were erroneously classified as EK, were comprised by features, such as

Content-Type: application/octet-stream, Content-Encoding, Jar file in the URL, Suspicious filename in the URL, and high Domain/Subdomain Entropy that typically appear in EK samples. Thus, EKnad in the old-EK dataset achieved higher FPR than Snort and Suricata. The findings of the fourth experiment indicate that EKnad performs better than Snort and Suricata in terms of detection of both old and new EKs. Even though the EK samples deployed in the experiment are publicly available, the EK rulesets are not sufficient enough to detect all EKs. Another interesting finding is that the community ruleset that was deployed in Snort is more robust on old EKs, while the ET open ruleset that deployed in Suricata is more effective on newer EKs. It is important to mention that both IDSs have commercially available rules (that we were not able to validate), which might provide a more robust detection of EKs.

6.5. Discussion

Based on the results of the experiments 1, 2, and 3, we concluded that MLP, in comparison to RF, BN, DT, KNN, and J48 classifiers, achieved the best detection performance, since it yielded the best results in all experiments. We deduce that MLP, overall, is the most efficient algorithm for the proposed EKnad. Furthermore, we draw the following generic conclusions:

1. MLP: The MLP classifier has proved to be the most suitable for the detection of EKs network activity. It misclassified the least EK samples in all experiment.
2. RF: The RF classifier achieved the second best results in all the experiments.
3. BN: The results of BN classifier in the second experiment were similar to RF, while in the first and third experiment its results were slightly worst than RF.
4. KNN: The KNN classifier yielded better results in the third experiment than BN (worst than MLP and RF), but in experiments 1 and 2 its results were worst than MLP, RF, and BN.
5. J48: The J48 classifier attained slightly better results than DT in all experiments and worst than MLP, RF, BN, and KNN.
6. DT: The DT classifier had the worst results of all the tested classifiers in all three experiments.

Regarding the results of the fourth experiment, Snort attained better results on older EKs, whilst Suricata performed better on newer EKs. On the other hand, EKnad with MLP classifier outperformed both Snort's and Suricata's detection capabilities, while accomplishing comparable results in terms of FPs.

Finally, a comparison with previous works is performed as shown in Table 7. In particular, we compared EKnad with previous works in terms of common evaluation metrics (e.g., accuracy and precision), detection category, number of EK families, whether they deployed imbalanced data, and whether they publicly share the datasets. As shown in Table 7, the numerical results of EKnad are similar and comparable with the results of previous works. However, even though some works attained high detection performance, the results cannot provide a comprehensive view of how these solutions will perform in real-world scenarios. That is, some previous works (e.g., [23], [24], [25], [15]) deploy balanced datasets, which is not realistic in

⁸<https://github.com/codecat007/snort-rules/tree/master/snortrules-snapshot-2983>

⁹https://rules.emergingthreats.net/OPEN_download_instructions.html

Table 7: Comparison with state-of-the-art. The "N", "S", and "C" indicate the network traffic, EK server-side, and EK client-side categories respectively (see Section 3).

Paper	ACC	Prec.	#EK Families	Imbalanced Data	Data Sharing	Detection Category
Mekky et al. [23]	0.99	0.95-0.99	N/A	✗	✗	N
Taylor et al. [24]	0.95	N/A	6	✗	✗	N
Nikolaev et al. [25]	N/A	0.92-0.95	3	✗	✗	N
Qin et al. [15]	0.95	0.96	N/A	✗	✗	N
Burgess et al. [14]	0.99	0.99	N/A	✓	✗	N
Harmetta [27]	0.98	N/A	5	✗	✗	N
Eshete et al. [29]	0.99	N/A	11	✓	✗	S
Kim et al. [34]	N/A	0.99	12	✓	✗	C
Yoo et al. [11]	0.98	N/A	11	✓	✗	C
EKnad	0.98-0.99	0.98-0.99	26	✓	✓	N

malware detection. In general, the majority of the related work has not considered the proposed rules of section 6.1 (i.e., A1-A5), and therefore, their results may be biased. Moreover, as one can notice in Table 7 some works (e.g., [29]) rely on the source code of EKs to detect malicious activity, which is not robust as obfuscation techniques can hinder detection. Moreover, we have considered a higher number of EK families (26 in total) compared to all other works. Finally, a drawback of the previous works is that they do not share enough information (e.g., datasets). Thus, their results are not reproducible. We have shared the deployed datasets to drive more research in the EK detection field as well as to assist researchers reproduce the results of EKnad and compare it with future solutions.

7. Conclusions

This paper proposed EKnad, a data-driven ML-based methodology for efficient EK detection. The methodology includes two phases: the *Pre-processing* and the *EK detection*. A rich feature set (47 features in total) that takes into account the whole infection procedure of EKs was proposed and analyzed comprehensively. Moreover, five comprehensive imbalanced datasets of packet capture files were created based on publicly available sources that include in total 26 different EK families. Four distinct experiments were carried out to extensively evaluate EKnad seeking to find the most efficient classifier for the proposed methodology with respect to state-of-the-art rules and guidelines to avoid misleading and erroneous results. The results of the first three experiments revealed that EKnad yields the best performance when the MLP classifier is employed with at least 0.065 FPR, 0.984 recall & precision, 0.983 F1-score, 0.949 MCC, 0.996 AUC, as well as a detection accuracy varied from 0.983 to 0.991 in all experiments. In this way, we deduced that EKnad was able to detect new and last-generation EKs based on the training of older EKs as well as less-known EK families based on the training of well-known EK families. The fourth experiment compared EKnad with two prominent open-source IDSs, Snort and Suricata. The results indicated that EKnad is more efficient than these two IDSs in terms of EK detection rate.

As EKs can readily extend or modify their delivery payload, they will remain a serious threat adapting their modus operandi to the latest malware trends. Since EKnad is a generic solution against EKs, we strongly believe that it will be able to detect not only present but also future EKs. EKnad can be easily incorporated into the traffic analysis and detection pipeline of corporate

networks to work in tandem with other security controls (e.g., antivirus) offering an in-depth defence approach and facilitating blue teams and network administrators to shield corporate networks against real-world EK attacks.

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